

Chetia brevis
Orange-fringed largemouth

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Bony fish

Size: 15 cm

Distribution:

Komati-Incomati River system, Mpumalanga, South Africa and coastal lakes in Mozambique.

Importance:

The historical distribution of the *Chetia brevis* included 85km of the Lomati tributary of the Incomati River. Due to invasive species and pollution, this population has crashed and can now only be found in a 2.5km stretch of the river system. This species is listed as endangered on the IUCN red list. A captive breeding project has been initiated to attempt to reseed the historical range of this species.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 93.98 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 4.14 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.86 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.2% [Single: 96.1%, Duplicated: 3.1%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 1 245.69 kilobases

Contig number: 13 656

Sample Contributor contact details:

Roger Bills

SAIAB

IR.Bills@saiab.nrf.ac.za

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